

Project JHI-E1-1 “Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: Pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs”

**Instructions for developing place-based scenarios in a workshop
Isle of Coll, Scotland, 17-18 February 2026**

These instructions refer to the agenda sessions specified below (from 6:55pm to 8:00pm).

Agenda item	Time	Activity
Workshop group discussion: Developing a ‘business-as-usual’ scenario for Coll for 2045	6:55pm - 7:30pm	Using the “drivers and outcomes table” and Lego bricks, workshop groups scope out a likely scenario for 2045 under normal conditions, responding to the question: <i>‘Given the current economic and policy landscape, including on housing, what do we think a likely scenario for Coll in 2045 is? What are the most relevant drivers of change? What will most probably happen?’</i>
		Groups vote the relevance of each "driver" for the future of Coll and, for each driver (if this was judged relevant), the most likely “outcome” in 2045. The facilitator narrates the "business-as-usual" scenario based on the votes.
Break	7:30pm - 7:40pm	Refreshments
Workshop group discussion: What is your ideal vision for Coll in 2045? Where could a local housing policy help achieve this?	7:40pm - 8:00pm	Using the “drivers and outcomes table” and Lego bricks (without removing the previous votes, as the relevance won’t be voted again), workshop groups scope out a desirable scenario for 2045, responding to the question: <i>‘What would be the most desirable outcome for each driver of change for Coll in 2045? What would you like to see in an ideal future?’</i> The facilitator narrates the ideal scenario based on the votes.
		Using the “drivers and outcomes table” and Lego bricks (without removing the previous votes), workshop groups identify the drivers of change that could be impacted by a housing policy, responding to the question: <i>‘Which of these drivers do you think are influenced by housing? Does housing determine whether we move towards the most likely or the most desirable outcome?’</i>

Logistics. Workshop participants must be divided into **tables** of a maximum of 5-6 participants, possibly located not too close to each other in the room, in order to avoid interferences (the discussions must evolve autonomously to maximise the amount of information collected). Each table will be managed by two Hutton researchers, hereafter the “**lead**” (who facilitates the conversation), and the “**supporter**” (who deals with the logistics, and takes notes).

Material. For each table, the following **items** are required:

- Sticky dots of two different colours to allocate people to the tables.
- A large enough table (or tables) for the A0 poster to stay on it.
- Seven chairs for people to sit in case they get tired.
- An A0 laminated poster illustrating the drivers of change and the potential outcomes (Figure 1).
- Six Lego walls including eight bricks of each of four different colours (Figure 2).
- A red marker, a green marker, and a black marker which can write on a laminated poster.
- A notepad and pen for taking further notes.
- Post-it notes to write down the main emerging ideas.
- Eight A4 sheets of paper to cover the outcomes while we vote the relevance of the drivers.
- Strong tape to fix the poster to the table, and blue tack to fix the A4 sheets on the poster.
- A voice recorder.

Figure 1. Poster of “drivers and outcomes” to be put on the table to derive the scenarios.

Figure 2. Lego wall to be used for expressing the votes.

Preparation stage. As soon as people arrive at the venue, they are assigned to one of the two tables by being given a sticky dot of a different colour for each table. In order for the allocation to be random, the person welcoming the participants must alternate the sticky dots provided, also making sure that the two participants from the Argyll & Bute Council are assigned to different tables.

The tables must be pre-set by putting the A0 poster on them, fixing it with strong tape to ensure that it stays flat and the Lego bricks do not move when voting, and covering the outcomes of the drivers with blank A4 sheets of papers fixed with blue tack. The laptop must be placed on the side of the table facing the top of the poster, with the Excel file open on it (and making sure that the battery is well charged to last for around one hour). The voice recorder must be activated by the supporter before the participants get to the table, and put on the table in a position where it can record the whole conversation with minimum interference during the voting process (i.e., not on the poster).

6:55-7:10. Introduction. As soon as the researcher leading the “*Overview of key challenges, potential solutions and policy*” closes that session, the supporter activates the voice recorder and puts it on the table, while the lead invites the participants who have been assigned to their table to come around the table. The lead and the supporter must position themselves on the side of the table facing the top of the poster, so that participants can read the drivers’ and outcomes’ names more easily by staying on the other sides. People must be asked not to sit unless they get tired, to allow others to move around.

Once all the participants have taken their position around the table, the lead explains the goal of the session: *“Thanks again for attending this workshop. The goal of this session is to develop a likely scenario for Coll for 2045. This scenario refers to Coll as a place, its community and economy, not to a specific sector. For this purpose, we will use a so-called table of drivers and local outcomes, that our research team has developed within a large European project, where it has been used across 33 European localities. We have reviewed the table based on studies concerning Scotland’s rural and island areas, and in the light of the priorities of Coll’s Local Place Plan, kindly provided by Coll’s Community Council. The result is the image that you see on the table. How does it work? First, we have identified eight drivers of change that affect rural and island places, for example technological change, and climate & natural resources [do not name the first ones, otherwise they get too much visibility]. In the next 20 years, each of these drivers can move in several directions, reaching different potential local outcomes. A scenario is a combination of the movements of all the drivers; some drivers can be irrelevant for Coll, and therefore their outcome does not matter. To determine the likely scenario for Coll, we need to agree on the relevance of the drivers, and the likelihood of their outcomes. As the first step, we will focus on the relevance of the drivers, so their outcomes have been provisionally covered. Each of you have received some Lego bricks of different colours: we will use them to express votes. Before I explain how the vote takes place, are there any questions concerning what I have said so far?”* [Answer questions; if something is to be explained later, tell them so.]

“Thanks for your questions. The relevance of the drivers indicates how impactful the driver is for the future of Coll, that is, how much difference it makes whether it will move in one direction or another. To vote the relevance, we use the white bricks of Lego, by putting above the box that contains the name of a driver. You have eight of these white bricks. If you think that all drivers are relevant, you put one brick on each of the names; if you think that some are not relevant, while others are very relevant, you can put no bricks on the former, and more than one brick on the latter: this is your choice, but you must use all your white bricks. If you put more than one brick on the same driver, or if other people have already put some of their bricks on that driver, please connect the bricks together to create a wall. Is the procedure for the voting of the relevance clear enough?” [Answer questions.]

Since the explanation of the drivers can be quite long and tedious, the lead must assess whether it is the case of providing detailed explanations also based on the questions received from the audience. In case explanations are needed, below is a table listing the two elements that constitute each driver, with some details concerning each of them. Please say the following: *“We know that some drivers may have been overlooked. Of course, the reality is much more complex, but we needed to keep complexity at a manageable level. Are all the drivers clear enough, or would you want me to clarify some of them?”* [Answer questions.]

Driver	Element 1	Element 2
1. Demographic trends	Young people return after education. <i>It indicates whether the young people who leave Coll for studying will be more or less likely than today to return and live on the island.</i>	People move to Coll and become resident. <i>It indicates whether there will be more or less people not originally from Coll moving to live on the island.</i>
2. Housing market	Availability of affordable housing to rent. <i>It indicates whether the number of houses available in Coll for rent by residents will increase or decrease.</i>	Restrictiveness of planning regulations. <i>It indicates whether building new houses for residents will become easier or more difficult due to planning regulations.</i>
3. Climate & natural resources	Restrictiveness of conservation regulations. <i>It indicates whether regulations for nature conservation will become more or less restrictive, thus affecting</i>	Climate and extreme events. <i>It indicates whether, as a result of climate change, the climate will become more unpredictable, with frequent extreme events, or</i>

	<i>land- and resource-based economic activities, such as farming.</i>	<i>milder, which entails for example a longer growing season.</i>
4. Tourism sector	Number of tourists. <i>It indicates whether the number of people coming to Coll for tourism will increase or decrease.</i>	Use of houses as holiday homes. <i>It indicates whether tourists will rely mostly on holiday homes, competing with potential residents looking for homes, or there will be more diverse accommodation solutions, like camping, hotels, hostels, etc.</i>
5. Technological change	Quality of internet connectivity. <i>It indicates whether the quality of the internet connectivity, wherever one lives on Coll, will improve or stay the same.</i>	Online delivery of public services. <i>It indicates whether the delivery of public services (e.g., medical appointments, schooling, etc.) will worsen, or improve thanks to online delivery.</i>
6. Devolution & participation	Number of local volunteers. <i>It indicates whether the participation by Coll people, including new residents, to community life – primarily volunteering – will increase or decrease.</i>	Political centralisation/devolution. <i>It indicates whether as a result of evolving governance patterns at Scotland’s level, rural and island communities will receive more regulatory and policy powers, or we will see increasing centralisation of decision-making in Edinburgh.</i>
7. Transport infrastructure	Quality of ferry services. <i>It indicates whether the availability, reliability, and affordability of ferry services to Coll will improve or decline.</i>	On-island movement. <i>It indicates whether on-island movement will become easier, for example thanks to the introduction of various forms of public transport and good road maintenance, or more difficult due to the deterioration of the existing road infrastructure.</i>
8. Job market	Availability of online (remote) jobs. <i>It indicates whether remote job opportunities, allowing to work from Coll for an employer located elsewhere, will increase, or decrease.</i>	Local business providing employment. <i>It indicates whether the number of businesses (shops, farms, etc.) based in Coll, and providing employment opportunities locally, will increase or decrease.</i>

7:10-7:18. Vote on the relevance. After having possibly provided some explanation of the drivers, the lead says the following: *“Let us proceed with the vote of the relevance. The question we are trying to answer is the following: ‘Given the current economic and policy landscape, including on housing, what do we think the most relevant drivers of change for Coll between now and 2045 will be?’ Please start voting by putting your white Lego bricks on the names of the relevant drivers, as explained. You have five minutes: feel free to exchange opinions if you want. I will tell you when we have one minute left.”* [Start counting the time. If there are questions, answer them, but be careful not to suggest what to vote. Tell when one minute is left, and then when five minutes have passed, continue speaking.] *“Thanks for voting. While [name of the supporter] counts your votes, I will explain how the likelihood of the outcomes will be voted.”* [The supporter takes one photo of the poster with the votes, just in case the Legos are moved by mistake.] *“The most relevant drivers are [name driver(s) that possibly stand out, if any], while [name driver(s) with zero votes, if any] were judged not relevant for Coll.”* OR *“All drivers were judged relevant, with limited differences.”*

7:18-7:30. Vote on the likelihood. The lead continues speaking: *“Thanks for voting the relevance of the drivers. Now, we need to determine the likelihood of the outcomes of the relevant drivers given the current economic and policy landscape. We will proceed one driver at a time, starting from the most relevant. [The lead uncovers the most relevant driver by removing the A4 sheet.] Each driver can move towards one of four potential outcomes. Again, some of the outcomes may look oversimplistic, and some potential outcomes may have been overlooked. In particular, the elements are assumed to move in opposite directions rather than staying as they are. Of course, the reality is much more*

complex, but we needed to keep complexity at a manageable level. If some drivers are not moving in a clear-cut direction, it will emerge as part of the later steps. If you would like to comment on some of the outcomes, or ask for clarification, please do not hesitate to do so, and [name of the supporter] will write down your thoughts on post-it notes and attach them to the related outcomes. [From now, the supporter must write down the main points concisely on post-it notes, and attach them on the poster.]

“The question we are trying to answer is as follows: ‘Given the current economic and policy landscape, including on housing, what will most probably happen in Coll in 2045 in terms of each of the relevant drivers of change?’ We will use the yellow Lego bricks. You must put one brick on the square describing the outcome that you consider more likely. [If some drivers have zero relevance votes, add: “The drivers [name(s) of driver(s)] were judged not relevant for Coll, therefore we won’t vote the likelihood of their outcomes, and some of the yellow bricks will remain with you.”] If other people have already put their bricks on the outcome that you would like to vote, please connect your brick to theirs. The Legos indicating relevance will remain on the poster, therefore please be careful not to move them. Before we proceed with the vote, is the procedure for the voting of the likelihood clear enough?” [Answer questions.]

“Let us proceed with the vote of the likelihood of the outcomes of the driver [name(s) of driver(s)]. Please put one of your Lego bricks on the outcome that you deem more likely. [The participants vote. After all participants have expressed their vote, the lead circles, using the red marker, the most likely outcome(s) of the driver. If two outcomes are equally likely, they draw a single, larger circle. Then, they say some words about the result of the vote: “Given the current economic and policy landscape, in 2045 Coll will see...” If for some drivers, the consensus is less clear, it must be mentioned.] Would you like to add anything? [The supporter writes down the main points concisely on post-it notes, and attaches them on the poster. The vote is repeated for each driver, until reaching the least relevant one that has obtained at least one relevance vote.]

7:30-7:40. Break. After all likely outcomes are circled, the lead announces the break: *“We have reached the end of this session. Now we will have a 10-minute break with refreshments, then we will reconvene here to discuss where we would like to be in 20 years. Please leave your remaining Lego bricks on the table, and be careful not to move the bricks put on the poster.”* [The recording is paused. While the participants have the break, the lead and the supporter take some photos of the poster with the votes, just in case the Legos are moved by mistake.]

7:40-7:50. Vote of the ideal vision. The lead and the supporter call the participants back to the table. They position themselves again on the side of the table where the top of the poster looks, and describe the goal of this new session: *“Thanks for your contribution until now. The goal of this new session is to develop an ideal vision for Coll for 2045. Again, this vision refers to Coll as a place, not to a specific sector. In the previous session, we have defined the relevance of the drivers of change, and the likelihood of their outcomes in the current economic and policy landscape. Now, we want to understand what the most desirable outcomes are. We have maintained the previous votes on the poster, to allow you to link this session to what happened during the previous one. This time, we will use the eight black Lego bricks. For each of the relevant drivers, you must put one brick on the outcome that you consider most desirable, which can also coincide with the most likely one. Before we vote, do you have any questions?”* [Answer questions.]

“Let us proceed with the vote of desirability. The question we are trying to answer is as follows: ‘What would be the most desirable outcome for the relevant drivers of change for Coll in 2045? What would you like to see in an ideal future?’ We will proceed one driver at a time, starting from the most relevant, which is [name(s) of driver(s)]. Please put one of your Lego bricks on the outcome that you deem more desirable. [The participants vote. After all participants have expressed their vote, the lead circles, using the green marker, the most desirable outcome(s) of the driver. If two outcomes are equally likely, they draw a single, larger circle. Unless the likely and desirable outcomes coincide, using the black

marker, they draw an arrow from the red to the green circles/shapes. Then, they say some words about the result of the vote: *“In an ideal future, the most desirable outcome for Coll in 2045 would be...”* If for some drivers the consensus is less clear, it must be mentioned.] *Would you like to add anything?* [The supporter writes down the main points concisely on post-it notes, and attaches them on the poster. The vote is repeated for each driver, until reaching the least relevant one. Then, the supporter takes one photo of the poster with the votes, just in case the Legos are moved by mistake.]

7:50-8:00. Vote on the impact of housing. The lead continues: *“Our research as well as previous research on rural Scotland have clearly highlighted that housing represents the most pressing challenge for rural communities. Besides identifying the most likely and the most desirable scenarios for Coll in 2045 and how they differ, the goal of this workshop is to determine whether a local housing policy could help us move from the former to the latter. The specific elements of the housing policy will be discussed in the next session. Now, we would like to understand which drivers are influenced by housing. For this last vote, we will use the red Lego bricks, by putting them at the centre of the four boxes detailing the outcomes. You have eight of these red bricks. If you think that all drivers are influenced by housing, you put one brick on each of them; if you think that some are not influenced, while others are, you can put no bricks on the former, and more than one brick on the latter: this is your choice, but you must use all your red bricks. [In the unlikely event in which all the likely outcomes and the desirable outcomes coincide, you can add the following: *“We are very happy to see that Coll is moving in the right direction, which suggests that no relevant policy changes are required in terms of housing.”*]*

“Let us proceed with the vote. The question we are trying to answer is: ‘Which of these drivers do you think are influenced by housing? Does housing determine whether we move towards the most likely or the most desirable outcome?’ You do not need to consider the drivers in a specific order, and you have three minutes. After you have cast your vote, you can move to the other side of the room for a final plenary discussion.” [Start counting the time; if some participants are taking longer than the allocated time, please encourage them to vote. After everyone has voted and left the session, stop the recording. Then, the supporter takes some final photos of the poster with the votes. Then, they take note of the drivers that are impacted by housing, to report to the plenary for the discussion. The Lego bricks are left on the posters to avoid disturbing during the following discussion, and only removed at the very end of the workshop.]

8:00-8:05. Introduction to the policy discussion. The supporters report the results of the vote concerning the impact of housing. One of them starts, then the second one (from the other table) mentions if their results are similar, or where they differ: *“Thanks all for your contribution to date. We found that a local housing policy could help us not only to improve the housing market, but also to move from ... to ...”* [List all the drivers whose outcome can be impacted by housing; if they are many, you can only mention the drivers that received the highest number of votes. Afterwards, the lead researcher facilitates the session.]

Contacts

Simone Piras, Simone.Piras@hutton.ac.uk

Scottish Government
Riaghaltas na h-Alba
gov.scot

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